

Strong Convergence Theorem for Finite Family of Asymptotically Nonexpansive in the Intermediate Sense Nonsself Maps

Agatha Chizoba Nnubia

Department of Mathematics Nnamdi Azikiwe University PMB 5025 Awka, Anambra State, Ngeria

Nkiruka Maria-Assumpta Akabuike

Department of Mathematics and Computer, Federal Polythemic Oke, Anambra State, Nigeria

Chika Moore

Department of Mathematics Nnamdi Azikiwe University PMB 5025 Awka, Anambra State, Ngeria

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Abstract:

Let K be a nonexpansive retract of a uniformly convex Banach space X with retraction P . Let $T_i: K \rightarrow X$ ($i=1, \dots, m$) be a finite family of **uniformly continuous asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense maps** with a nonempty common fixed points set F . Sufficient conditions for the strong convergence of a sequence of successive approximations generated by an m -step algorithm to a point of F are proved.

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Introduction

Let K be a nonempty subset of a normed linear space E . K is said to be (sequentially) compact if every bounded sequence in K has a subsequence that converges in K . K is said to be boundedly compact if every bounded subset of K is compact. In finite dimensional spaces, closed subsets are boundedly compact.

Given a subset S of K , we shall denote by $Co(S)$ and $ccl(S)$ the convex hull and the closed

convex hull of S respectively. If K is boundedly compact convex and S is bounded, then $co(S)$ and hence $ccl(S)$ are compact convex subsets of K .

A map $T: K \rightarrow E$ is said to be semi-compact if for any bounded sequence $\{x_n\}$ in K such that

$\|x_n - Tx_n\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ there exists a subsequence $\{x_{n_j}\}$ subset $\{x_n\}$

such that x_{n_j} converges strongly to some x^* in K as $j \rightarrow \infty$.

The map T is said to be demi-compact at z in E if for any bounded sequence $\{x_n\}$ subset K such that

$x_n - Tx_n \rightarrow z$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. there exist a subsequence $\{x_{n_j}\}$ subset $\{x_n\}$

and a point p in K such that x_{n_j} converges strongly to p as $j \rightarrow \infty$.

(Observe that if T is additionally continuous, then $p - Tp = z$).

A nonlinear map $T: K \rightarrow E$ is said to be completely continuous if it maps bounded sets into relatively compact sets. A mapping $T: K \rightarrow$

E is called *nonexpansive* if and only if for all x, y in K , we have that

$$\|Tx - Ty\| \leq \|x - y\| \quad (1)$$

K is called a *nonexpansive retract* of E if there exists a nonexpansive map $p: E \rightarrow K$ which is onto and such that $P^2 = I$. The map P is called the nonexpansive retraction of E onto K

The mapping T is called asymptotically nonexpansive mapping if and only if there exists a sequence $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $[0, +\infty)$, with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n = 0$ such that for all x, y in K ,

$$\|T(P^n)^{n-1}x - T(P^n)^{n-1}y\| \leq (1 + u_n) \|x - y\| \quad (2)$$

for all n in \mathbb{N} (set of natural number)

T is called *asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense* if and only if there exist two sequences $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{e_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $[0, +\infty)$, with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n = 0 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} e_n$ such that for all x, y in K .

$$\|T(P^n)^{n-1}x - T(P^n)^{n-1}y\| \leq (1 + u_n) \|x - y\| + e_n \quad n \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

T is called *Generalized asymptotically nonexpansive* if and only if there exist two sequences $\{\mu_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{\eta_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $[0, +\infty)$, with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu_n = 1$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \eta_n = 0$ such that for all x, y in K .

$$\|T(P^n)^{n-1}x - T(P^n)^{n-1}y\| \leq \mu_n \|x - y\| + \eta_n, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

The class of asymptotically nonexpansive mappings was introduced by Goebel and Kirk (1972) as a generalisation of nonexpansive mappings. The class of asymptotically

nonexpansive in the intermediate sense generalises the class of asymptotically nonexpansive mappings. As further generalisation, Alber, Chidume and Zegeye (2006) introduced the class of total asymptotically nonexpansive mappings, where a mapping $T: K \rightarrow H$ is called *total asymptotically nonexpansive* if and only if there exist two sequences $\{u_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{e_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $[0, +\infty)$, with $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n = 0 = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} e_n$ and a nondecreasing continuous function $Q: [0, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ with $Q(0) = 0$ such that for all x, y in K ,

$$\|T(P^n)^{n-1}x - T(P^n)^{n-1}y\| \leq \|x - y\| + u_n Q(\|x - y\|) + e_n \quad n \geq 1 \quad (5)$$

In Ofoedu and Nnubia (2014) an example to show that the class of asymptotically nonexpansive mappings is a proper subset of the class of total asymptotically nonexpansive mappings was given.

The class of total asymptotically nonexpansive type mappings includes the class of mappings which are asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense and Generalised asymptotically nonexpansive maps. These classes of mappings have been studied by several authors (see e.g. Goebel and Kirk (1972), Lim and Xu (1994), Alber et al (2008), Zegeye and Shahzad (2013), Nnubia and Bishop (2020)).

Preliminaries

We shall make use of the following in the sequel.

A Banach space E is said to satisfy Opial's condition if for each sequence $\{x_n\}$ subset E which converges weakly to a point z in E , we have that

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - z\| < \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - y\|, \quad \text{for all } y \text{ in } E; \quad y \text{ not equal to } z.$$

It is well known that every Hilbert space satisfies Opial's condition (Osilike & Shehu (2009))

A map T is said to satisfies **condition B** if there exists a continuous, strictly increasing function $f: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, with $f(0)=0$ such that for all x in $D(T)$, $\|x - Tx\| > f(d(x, F))$ where

$$F = F(T) = \{x \text{ in } D(T) : x = Tx\} \quad \text{and} \quad d(x, F) = \inf\{\|x - y\| : y \text{ in } F\}$$

Lemma 2.1 (Takahasi, 2000)

Let $\{a_n\}$ be sequence of nonnegative real numbers satisfying the following relation:

$$a_{n+1} \leq (1 - \alpha_n)a_n + \delta_n, \quad n > n_0,$$

where $\{\alpha_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $(0,1)$ and $\{\delta_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset \mathbb{R} (SET OF REAL NUMBER) satisfying the following conditions: $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \alpha_n = \infty$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$ and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \delta_n \leq 0$, then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n = 0$.

Lemma 2.2 (Moore & Nnoli, 2006)

Let $\{u_n\}$, $\{\mu_n\}$, $\{e_n\}$ be nonnegative sequences such that $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mu_n < \infty$, $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} e_n < \infty$, and

$$u_{n+1} \leq (1 + \mu_n)u_n + e_n. \text{ Then } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} u_n \text{ exists.}$$

Proposition 2.1

Suppose that there exist $c > 0, k > 0$ constants such that $Q(t) \leq c t$ for all $t \geq k$, then T is total asymptotically nonexpansive if and only if T is asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense.

Lemma 2.3

Let K be a closed convex nonempty subset of a Banach space E and let $T_i: K \rightarrow K$ where i in $I = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ be a finite family of continuous nonlinear maps in K such that $F = \prod_{i=1}^m F(T_i)$ is not empty and let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence in K satisfying

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T_i x_n\| = 0 \text{ for all } i \text{ in } I$$

there exist n_* in \mathbb{N} such that $\|x_{n+1} - x^*\| \leq (1 + \check{\alpha}_n) \|x_n - x^*\| + \mu_n$; for all $n > n_*$

where $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \mu_n < \infty$, and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \check{\alpha}_n < \infty$.

Then

1 $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\|$ exist and $\{x_n\}$ is bounded.

2 $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a common fixed point of T_i 's if and only if $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, F) = 0$.

3 $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a common fixed point of T_i 's if one of the T_i 's satisfies any of the following conditions:

(a) condition B (b) semi-compact, (d) demi compact at 0 in K , (e) completely continuous.

4 $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F if any of the following conditions holds:

(a) K is compact. (b) K is boundedly compact.

Proof: The proof of the Lemma 2.3 follows from Lemmas 2.6, 2.7, 2.8 and Remark 2.1 of Nnubia and Bishop(2020).

Results

Remark 3.1

By defining the sequence $\mu_n := 1 + u_n$, the family of generalized asymptotically nonexpansive mapping coincides with the family of asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense Mapping and hence from Theorems of Nnubia and Bishop (2020) we have the following corresponding theorems and corollaries for families of asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense Mapping.

Proposition 3.1

Let K be a nonexpansive retract of a Banach space X with nonexpansive retraction P . Let $T_i: K \rightarrow K$ in $I = \{1, \dots, m\}$ be a finite family of continuous asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense maps with sequences $\{u_{n,j}\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{e_{n,j}\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $[0, +\infty)$ such that $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{u_{n,j}\} < \infty$, $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{e_{n,j}\} < \infty$. Suppose that $F = \prod_{i=1}^m F(T_i)$ is not empty and let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence generated by

$x_n \in K; y_{\{n,0\}} = x_n, n \geq 0$

$$y_{\{n,i\}} = P[(1 - \alpha_{\{n\}})x_{\{n\}} + \alpha_{\{n\}}T_i(P_{T_i}^{\wedge^{n-1}})y_{\{n,i-1\}}],$$

$$y_{\{n,m\}} = x_{\{n+1\}} = y_{\{n+1\}} \quad 3.1$$

where $\{\alpha_{\{n\}}\}_{n \geq 1}$, is a sequence in $(0,1)$ such that $0 < a < \alpha_{\{n\}} < b < 1$ for all $n \geq 1$. Let x^* in F , then $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - x^*\|$ exist.

Theorem 3.1

Let K be a nonexpansive retract of a uniformly convex Banach space X with nonexpansive retraction P . Let $T_i: K \rightarrow E$ be a finite family of uniformly continuous asymptotically nonexpansive in the intermediate sense maps with sequences $\{u_{\{n,i\}}\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{e_{\{n,i\}}\}_{n \geq 1}$ subset $[0, +\infty)$ such that $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{u_{\{n,j\}}\} < \infty$, $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \{e_{\{n,j\}}\} < \infty$. Suppose that $F = \prod_{i=1}^m F(T_i)$ is not empty and let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence generated iteratively by (3.1),

where $\{\alpha_{\{n\}}\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a sequence in $(0,1)$ satisfying the following conditions: $0 < a < \alpha_{\{n\}} < b < 1$ for all $n \geq 1$, then for all i in $\{1,2,\dots,m\}$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n - T_i x_n\| = 0$.

Theorem 3.2

Let K, X, P, T_i 's, $F, \{x_n\}$ be as in Theorem 3.1

Then, $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a fixed point of T if and only if $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, F) = 0$.

Theorem 3.3

Let K, X, P, T_i 's, $F, \{x_n\}$ be as in Theorem 3.1

Then, $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a common fixed point of T_i 's if one of the T_i 's satisfies any of the following condition: (a) condition B (b). semi-compact (c). demi compact at 0 in K , (d). completely continuous.

Theorem 3.4

Let K, X, P, T_i 's, $F, \{x_n\}$ be as in Theorem 3.1, then, $\{x_n\}$ converges strongly to a point of F if

(a) K is compact. (b). K is boundedly compact.

Conclusion

Our iterative process generalizes some of the existing ones, our theorems improve, unify and extend several known results and our method of proof is of independent interest.

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